

Research Article

Smart Medical Bassinet: A Revolutionary Solution for Infant Safety and Monitoring

Fatimah Sham¹, Noraini Hashim^{2*}, Roswati Nordin³, Wan Marina Wan Ismail⁴, and Norhaini Majid⁵

¹ Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, 42300 Bandar Puncak Alam Selangor, Malaysia; fatimah2886@uitm.edu.my 0000-0002-5607-5760

² Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, 42300 Bandar Puncak Alam Selangor, Malaysia; hnoraini@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0003-0077-7584

³ Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, 42300 Bandar Puncak Alam Selangor, Malaysia; roswati2809@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0001-8108-6197

⁴ Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, 42300 Bandar Puncak Alam Selangor, Malaysia; wanmarina@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-6735-5912

⁵ Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, 42300 Bandar Puncak Alam Selangor, Malaysia; norhaini046@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0000-7696-3784

* Correspondence: hnoraini@uitm.edu.my; +60323584346

Abstract: Neonatal care presents numerous challenges, including the prevention of hypothermia, effective monitoring of vital signs, and ensuring comfort for both caregivers and postnatal mothers. Current bassinets often lack the integrated functionality required to meet these demands comprehensively. The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET addresses these gaps with an innovative, multifunctional design that enhances neonatal care through real-time monitoring, ergonomic solutions, and ease of use. The bassinet offers key features such as a built-in weight scale, temperature sensors, and motion-activated LED lighting. These tools assist healthcare professionals by continuously monitoring the baby's health, especially for premature infants. The ergonomic design, featuring height adjustability and narrow body construction, supports caregivers, particularly those with back or spinal issues, by allowing them to work in a standing position. For postnatal mothers, particularly those recovering from cesarean sections, the height adjustability feature facilitates easy access to their babies from the bedside, fostering bonding while ensuring safety and comfort. The impacts of this innovation are significant. The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET improves infant outcomes by preventing conditions such as hypothermia and providing early detection of weight loss. It reduces the workload for healthcare staff by streamlining routine tasks, allowing them to focus more on direct care. The intelligent design also promotes better visibility and eye contact between caregiver and infant, improving the overall caregiving experience. Regarding commercialization, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET has strong potential in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs), maternity wards, and pediatric healthcare facilities. Its versatile, holistic design addresses critical gaps in neonatal care while improving workplace ergonomics, making it a valuable investment for hospitals aiming to elevate service quality and enhance patient outcomes.

Keywords: Neonatal care, Infant monitoring, Ergonomic medical bassinet

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Neonatal care is one of the most critical stages in healthcare, as newborns are highly vulnerable during the first days and weeks of life. Despite technological advancements, there remain significant challenges in providing optimal care, particularly in maintaining body temperature, monitoring vital signs, and ensuring the comfort of both healthcare workers and parents (Kyokan et al., 2021).

Traditional bassinets commonly used in hospitals fall short of addressing these needs comprehensively. They often lack built-in systems for continuously monitoring vital signs, temperature regulation, and features that support caregivers' ergonomic needs and parents' accessibility (Lunze et al., 2013). This highlights the urgent need for an innovative solution combining medical functionality with ergonomic design.

Hypothermia, a leading cause of neonatal complications, exemplifies the risks associated with inadequate monitoring equipment (Lunze et al., 2013). Traditional bassinets, being static, limit caregivers' ability to respond efficiently to newborns, especially for those with physical strain or spinal issues (Sydor et al., 2022). Postnatal mothers, particularly those recovering from cesarean sections, face further difficulties with traditional bassinets due to the lack of height adjustability, which complicates handling and bonding with their babies (Nara Bassinet by Tekna, 2019). These challenges underscore the necessity for an advanced solution that integrates technology and ergonomic considerations.

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET directly addresses these issues. It combines essential features like a built-in weight scale, temperature monitoring probe, and LED lighting, ensuring newborns are in a safe, monitored environment. Ergonomically designed with adjustable height and soft casters, it provides healthcare workers ease of use across various settings, such as neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and general pediatric wards. Additionally, the bassinet promotes mother-infant bonding through enhanced accessibility, making it both a medical and user-friendly solution.

Given its multifunctional capabilities, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET holds strong commercialization potential. It addresses the hospital's need for improved efficiency, reduced error, and better patient care. Its real-time monitoring features help healthcare professionals prevent complications like hypothermia, while its portability and adaptability enhance its utility across various hospital settings. As hospitals increasingly invest in advanced technology, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET stands out as a practical, necessary solution that modernizes neonatal care.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET was developed through a structured approach to address key gaps in neonatal care. The method involved incorporating feedback from healthcare workers, including nurses and doctors, to ensure the bassinet meets the practical needs of caregivers and postnatal mothers, particularly those recovering from surgical deliveries (Fuerch et al., 2019).

2.1 Design Process

The bassinet was designed with three core principles: ergonomic functionality, real-time infant monitoring, and user-friendliness. The design includes a narrow body and adjustable height to allow mothers, especially those post-cesarean, to bring their babies close to the bedside. This feature promotes mother-infant bonding and reduces physical strain, making it easier for mothers to handle their newborns without getting out of bed.

Additionally, the bassinet's height adjustability was developed to support healthcare workers, particularly those who experience spinal issues or back pain, by allowing them to work in a standing position. This ergonomic feature improves visibility and eye contact during infant care, enhancing the caregiving experience.

2.2 Materials

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET is made from acrylonitrile butadiene sterile (ABS) for easy cleaning and durability. The basket is constructed using Bisphenol A (BPA)-free polymer plastic, ensuring the newborn's safety while maintaining the product's structural integrity. The bassinet includes LED lighting with motion sensors around the basket, providing nighttime visibility without disturbing the infant.

One of the standout features of the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET is its comprehensive approach to ensuring the safety and well-being of newborns through continuous monitoring and user-friendly design elements. The inclusion of a temperature monitoring system is particularly vital, as neonatal hypothermia remains a significant concern in infant care. Hypothermia can lead to serious complications, and early detection is crucial to prevent these outcomes. The bassinet's built-in temperature detector probe continuously tracks the baby's body temperature, providing real-time data to healthcare professionals. This ensures that any deviations from the normal temperature range are immediately addressed, reducing the risk of hypothermia-related complications (Figure 1).

Another key feature is the integrated digital weighing scale, strategically placed beneath the bassinet. This scale enables healthcare workers to monitor the baby's weight without moving the infant to a separate weighing station, which can be disruptive and stressful, particularly for premature infants. Continuous weight monitoring is essential for premature babies, as weight fluctuations can indicate underlying health issues that require immediate attention. By integrating this functionality into the bassinet, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET streamlines the process, allowing healthcare professionals to track weight with minimal handling, thus reducing the risk of discomfort or harm

The bassinet is equipped with LED lighting featuring motion sensors to enhance usability further. These lights provide much-needed visibility in low-light or nighttime settings, ensuring that mothers and healthcare workers can check on the infant without turning on harsh overhead lights. This feature is especially beneficial during nighttime care, where maintaining a calm and quiet environment is crucial for the baby's rest and the mother's recovery. The motion sensors allow for hands-free operation, making it convenient and efficient for caregivers to monitor the baby while reducing disruptions to both the mother and the newborn (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Product illustration

A	Basket	H	Retractable work surface
B	Mattress	I	Narrow base cabinet

C	Reposition handle	J	Steer locks, green
D	High adjustment bar	K	Caster locks, red
E	Chart holder	L	5" extra soft-wheel caster
F	Two-tier drawers	M	Led light
G	Transport handle		

2.3 Testing and Evaluation

Prototypes are tested in simulated clinical environments to assess the usability of the bassinet by healthcare workers, focusing on functionality, mobility, and safety. Feedback from nurses, doctors, and parents is incorporated into iterative improvements, ensuring the final product meets the diverse needs of neonatal units.

3. FINDINGS

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET significantly improves neonatal care through its advanced features and user-friendly design. In prototype testing, healthcare professionals found the bassinet to be highly effective in reducing complications like neonatal hypothermia due to its integrated temperature monitoring system. The built-in weight scale simplifies daily routines, allowing healthcare workers to monitor the infant's growth without transferring them to separate equipment, which reduces handling risks.

The ergonomic design proved beneficial in improving workflow efficiency. Adjustable height and retractable work surfaces made it easier for nurses and doctors to perform essential tasks while maintaining a safe and comfortable environment for newborns and mothers. Including LED lighting with motion sensors allows for non-intrusive night care, enhancing convenience in dimly lit hospital wards

Figure 2. Side view.

Figure 3. Back view.

Figure 4. Top view.

Figure 5. Side view with tilt basket.

Figure 6. Top view with tilt basket.

3.1 Benefits

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET offers numerous critical benefits, starting with its ability to provide continuous, real-time health monitoring, which greatly enhances the safety and well-being of newborns. This smart feature allows healthcare professionals to closely monitor vital signs, particularly body temperature, thus reducing the risk of life-threatening conditions such as hypothermia—a persistent concern in neonatal units worldwide. The temperature monitoring system enables immediate detection of any irregularities, allowing for rapid intervention and minimizing the potential for serious complications.

For healthcare professionals, the bassinet's real-time monitoring reduces workload by automating key aspects of neonatal care. It improves response times to medical emergencies, making it easier for nurses, doctors, and caregivers to provide timely and effective care without the need for constant manual checks. The built-in weighing scale further streamlines care by allowing baby weight measurements to be taken directly at the bedside, enhancing efficiency and reducing the physical strain associated with moving infants to separate weighing stations.

For parents, particularly postnatal mothers recovering from surgical procedures like cesarean sections, the bassinet's ergonomic design ensures easy access to their baby from the bedside, promoting bonding and emotional connection without compromising safety. The height-adjustable design also allows for optimal visibility and eye contact, which is crucial for fostering early mother-infant bonding. Moreover, its narrow build and built-in storage enhance convenience, keeping baby essentials within easy reach.

3.2 Novelty and uniqueness

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET stands out for its innovative design, offering four key elements of novelty and uniqueness that set it apart from traditional bassinets. First, the ergonomic design is a breakthrough feature, combining height adjustability with a narrow body and integrated drawers. This design allows healthcare workers and parents to adjust the bassinet to a comfortable height, reducing strain and improving accessibility. The narrow body ensures the bassinet can be easily maneuvered around hospital rooms, making it ideal for tight spaces in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and general pediatric wards.

Second, the bassinet features a built-in digital weighing scale underneath the basket, enabling healthcare workers to monitor the infant's weight without moving them to a separate station. This feature simplifies the weighing process, reducing handling risks, particularly for premature or delicate newborns. It also streamlines workflows for nurses and doctors, allowing them to conduct weight checks quickly and efficiently during routine clinical rounds.

The third innovative feature is the temperature detector probe, which continuously monitors the baby's body temperature. This is crucial for preventing conditions like hypothermia or hyperthermia, which are common in neonatal units. By ensuring constant temperature monitoring, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET helps reduce the risk of neonatal complications and improves overall care quality.

Finally, the bassinet is equipped with LED lighting with motion sensors around the internal side of the basket. This feature enhances nighttime visibility, allowing caregivers and parents to check on the baby in low-light environments without disrupting the infant's sleep. The motion-activated lights ensure that the bassinet is functional, energy-efficient, and user-friendly. These novel features collectively make the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET a cutting-edge solution, addressing practical and safety concerns in neonatal care with enhanced functionality and convenience.

3.3 Commercialization Potential

The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET holds significant commercialization potential as a pioneering product in maternal and neonatal care services. Its innovative design, which evolves from traditional bassinets, addresses critical gaps in neonatal care with advanced technological features that enhance both efficiency and patient outcomes. This smart bassinet integrates cutting-edge functionalities such as continuous temperature monitoring, an embedded digital weighing scale, and ergonomic features, making it a highly attractive investment for hospitals and healthcare facilities worldwide.

With healthcare systems continually seeking technologies that improve care quality while optimizing operational efficiency, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET stands out as a versatile product suitable for a range of settings, including labor and delivery rooms, postnatal care units, neonatal intensive care units (NICUs), and general pediatric wards. Its multifunctional design not only improves the care experience for newborns but also eases the workload of healthcare workers by automating key monitoring processes and reducing physical strain with its ergonomic features. This broad applicability increases its market appeal across multiple departments within healthcare facilities.

Moreover, as the global demand for smart healthcare solutions rises, the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET is well-positioned to capture a significant market share in both developed and emerging healthcare markets. Hospitals investing in advanced technologies will likely adopt this product to enhance neonatal care outcomes, reduce human error, and streamline workflows. The product's

potential to reduce neonatal complications, such as hypothermia, and to improve overall neonatal care makes it a valuable asset for healthcare providers focused on delivering high-quality, safe care.

4. DISCUSSION

The commercialization of the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET presents a compelling opportunity to enhance neonatal care, but it also raises important considerations about its scalability and adoption in healthcare settings (Gellasch et al., 2023). Neonatal hypothermia, which affects a significant number of newborns globally, remains a preventable cause of infant mortality (Demtse et al., 2020). The SMART MEDICAL BASSINET directly addresses this issue with its built-in temperature monitoring system, offering a technologically advanced solution for early detection and prevention of hypothermia. The integration of real-time health monitoring ensures that healthcare professionals can intervene more rapidly, improving survival rates and health outcomes, particularly in critical care settings like the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU)(Nadkarni & Sakhuja., 2023).

However, despite these clear benefits, challenges to widespread adoption may arise. One argument against rapid commercialization is the potential cost implications for hospitals, particularly in low-resource settings. Advanced technology can be expensive to implement and maintain, which might limit the market to well-funded healthcare systems (Metty et al., 2023). Hospitals in developing countries or those with budget constraints might struggle to afford the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET, even though the need is greatest in such environments. To mitigate this, manufacturers could explore tiered pricing models or collaborate with global health organizations to subsidize costs.

On the other hand, the long-term cost savings due to increased efficiency and reduced infant mortality rates cannot be overlooked. Studies have shown that technologies improving workflow efficiency, like the ergonomic features of the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET, lead to better staff performance and patient outcomes (El-Sherbeeney et al, 2023). In addition, reducing handling risks by integrating features like the built-in weight scale enhances infant safety, further supporting the case for its commercialization.

In conclusion, while initial costs may pose barriers, the long-term benefits of the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET in improving neonatal outcomes and healthcare efficiency make it a valuable innovation. Strategic partnerships and flexible pricing models could ensure its adoption across diverse healthcare settings, making it a significant asset in neonatal care globally.

5. CONCLUSION

The smart medical bassinet represents a transformative innovation in neonatal care, addressing critical gaps in infant safety, monitoring, and healthcare efficiency. By integrating real-time temperature monitoring, a built-in weight scale, and ergonomic features, this bassinet enhances the quality of care for newborns while reducing the workload for healthcare professionals. Its multifunctional design ensures the prevention of conditions like neonatal hypothermia and promotes bonding between mother and child, improving overall patient satisfaction.

The potential for commercialization is significant as hospitals increasingly seek innovative technologies that improve patient outcomes and streamline operations. While initial costs may present challenges, particularly for resource-limited settings, the long-term benefits in reducing infant mortality, enhancing healthcare workflows, and cutting operational costs justify the investment.

Strategic partnerships and tiered pricing models can further aid in making this essential tool accessible across various healthcare environments.

In conclusion, the smart medical bassinet offers a comprehensive solution that has the potential to revolutionize neonatal care globally. It is a critical tool for improving newborn health and advancing healthcare professionals' capabilities in delivering efficient, high-quality care.

Acknowledgements: We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Centre for Nursing Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Kampus Puncak Alam, for their support in developing the SMART MEDICAL BASSINET. Special thanks to Madam Fatimah Binti Sham for her invaluable guidance throughout this project. We also extend our appreciation to the dedicated healthcare professionals who provided critical insights that shaped the design and functionality of this innovative product.

References

- Bassinnet, N. (2019). Nara Bassinet -by Tekna. Retrieved January 26, 2023, from <https://designawards.core77.com/CommercialEquipment/60622/Nara-Bassinnet>
- Demtse, A. G., Pfister, R. E., Nigussie, A. K., McClure, E. M., Ferede, Y. G., Tazu Bongor, Z., Mekasha, A., Demisse, A. G., Gidi, N. W., Metaferia, G., Worku, B., Goldenberg, R. L., & Muhe, L. M. (2020). Hypothermia in preterm newborns: Impact on survival. *Global Pediatric Health*, 7, 2333794X20957655. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2333794X20957655>
- El-Sherbeeney, A. M., Al-Romeedy, B. S., Abd elhady, M. H., Sheikhelsouk, S., Alsetoohy, O., Liu, S., & Khairy, H. A. (2023). How is job performance affected by ergonomics in the tourism and hospitality industry? Mediating roles of work engagement and talent retention. *Sustainability*, 15(20), 14947. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152014947>
- Fuerch, J. H., Sanderson, P., Barshi, I., & Liley, H. (2019). Developing safe devices for neonatal care. *Seminars in Perinatology*, 43(8), 151176. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.semperi.2019.08.005>
- Gellasch, P., Johnson, S., & Walsh, T. A. (2023). The experiences and perceptions of neonatal clinicians when using a responsive bassinet. *Advances in Neonatal Care*, 23(4), E88-E95. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ANC.0000000000001086>
- Kyokan, M., Jirapaet, V., Rosa-Mangeret, F., Pisoni, G., & Pfister, R. (2021). Gaps in neonatal thermal care in low-resource settings: A web-based survey of healthcare workers. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-980430/v1>.
- Lunze, K., Bloom, D. E., Jamison, D. T., & Hamer, D. H. (2013). The global burden of neonatal hypothermia: Systematic review of a major challenge for newborn survival. *BMC Medicine*, 11(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-11-24>
- Metty Paul, Maglaras, L., Ferrag, M. A., & Almomani, I. (2023). Digitization of the healthcare sector: A study on privacy and security concerns. *ICT Express*, 9(4), 571-588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ict.2023.02.007>
- Nadkarni, G. N., & Sakhuja, A. (2023). Clinical informatics in critical care medicine. *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine*, 96(3), 397-405. <https://doi.org/10.59249/WTTU3055>
- Sydor, M., Pop, J., Jasińska, A., & Zabłocki, M. (2022). Anthro-Mechanical Cradles: A Multidisciplinary Review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(23), 15759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192315759>